

Kinetics and Mechanism of Uncatalysed and Mercury(II)-catalysed Alkaline Chloramine-T Oxidation of Aspartic Acid

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Manuscript received 17 February 1986, revised 18 May 1987, accepted 11 August 1987

Kinetics of oxidation of aspartic acid by chloramine-T in aqueous sodium hydroxide media in absence and in presence of Hg^{II} has been investigated. A first order dependence each on chloramine-T and aspartic acid, both in absence and in presence of Hg^{II} has been observed. An inverse first order dependence on sodium hydroxide concentration has been established for both uncatalysed and catalysed oxidation reactions. Hg^{II} ions catalyse the reaction significantly and the catalytic action of Hg^{II} is ascribed to the complex formation with aspartic acid anions. A negligible salt-effect points to a mechanism involving a neutral molecule and anion in the rate determining step. The activation parameters for both uncatalysed and Hg^{II} -catalysed oxidations have also been computed. Rate laws consistent with the experimental results have been deduced and suitable mechanism has been proposed.

ORGANIC reagent, chloramine-T, having redox potential 0.499 V^1 at pH 12, has been employed to oxidise some typical amino acids in alkaline media^{2,3}. The biological significance of catalytic function of transition metal ions and their complex formation with amino acids has fascinated a few chemists to investigate the mechanistic aspects of transition metal ions catalysed chloramine-T oxidation of amino acids⁴⁻⁷. The present work is an attempt to investigate the oxidation mechanism of aspartic acid by alkaline chloramine-T in absence and in presence of Hg^{II} as catalyst.

Experimental

The concentration of aqueous chloramine-T (E. Merck, G.R.) was checked iodometrically⁸. The solution of aspartic acid (AnalaR) was always prepared afresh in conductivity water. All other reagents were of analytical grade.

Reaction mixtures were brought to thermostatic temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) and the reaction was started by adding the appropriate volume of chloramine-T. The progress of reaction was followed by estimating

unconsumed chloramine-T iodometrically. Owing to the high concentration of the alkali, there was no change in pH during the progress of the reaction.

Results

Chloramine-T dependence: To determine the dependence of the reaction rate on chloramine-T, consequently the order of the reaction, both in absence and in presence of Hg^{II} , the reaction was carried out at different concentrations of chloramine-T by keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant. The reaction follows the first order dependence at all the concentrations of chloramine-T. The results are enlisted in Table 1.

A comparison of both the rate constants indicates that the overall rate is enhanced considerably in presence of Hg^{II} ions.

Aspartic acid dependence: To determine the order of reaction with respect to reducing substrate in absence and in presence of Hg^{II} , the reaction was studied with different concentrations of aspartic acid. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 1

[Aspartic acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, [NaOH] = $8.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp. = 85°

	[Chloramine T] ($\times 10^3 \text{ M}$)									
	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$	1.60	1.62	1.58	1.69	1.61	1.61	1.74	1.61	1.60	1.81
$k' (\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})^a$	8.77	8.62	8.52	8.62	8.52	8.45	8.53	8.52	8.54	8.55

^a First order rate constant for Hg^{II} -catalysed reaction at $[\text{HgCl}_2] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

TABLE 2

[Chloramine-T] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [NaOH] = 8.0×10^{-2} M,
Temp. = 35°

[Aspartic acid] $\times 10^3$ M	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$10k$ [Aspartic acid] $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	k^* $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$10k^*$ [Aspartic acid]
0.9	1.42	1.58	3.27	3.69
1.0	1.61	1.61	3.52	3.52
1.1	1.79	1.62	3.77	3.42
1.2	2.01	1.67	4.40	3.66
1.3	2.27	1.74	4.86	3.74
1.4	2.47	1.76	5.23	3.78
1.5	2.75	1.88	5.50	3.66
1.6	2.98	1.86	5.87	3.67
1.7	3.14	1.84	6.22	3.65
1.8	3.29	1.82	6.54	3.63

* First order rate constant for Hg^{II}-catalysed reaction at [HgCl₂] = 4.0×10^{-4} M

The first order rate constants are found to be directly proportional to the concentration of substrate in both uncatalysed (Fig. 1) and Hg^{II}-catalysed reaction (Fig. 2.) The overall bimolecular rate constants for uncatalysed and Hg^{II}-catalysed oxidation showed fairly concordant values at all concentrations of reducing substrate.

Sodium hydroxide dependence - Sodium hydroxide dependence was studied by taking fixed concentrations of chloramine-I and aspartic acid and varying the concentration of sodium hydroxide over the range $5.6 - 9.2 \times 10^{-2}$ M. The findings in

Fig. 1. Plots of (a) k vs [Asp. acid], (b) $k/[\text{Asp. acid}]$ vs [Asp. acid] (uncatalysed).

Fig. 2. Plots of (a) k' vs [Asp. acid], (b) $k'/[\text{Asp. acid}]$ vs [Asp. acid] (Hg^{II}-catalysed).

absence and in presence of Hg^{II} are recorded in Table 3.

The product of [NaOH] and first order rate constant for both uncatalysed and Hg^{II}-catalysed oxidation reaction, at their perceptible alkali concentration range, gives almost constant values. This suggests an inverse first order in sodium hydroxide concentration. The plots of $1/k$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $1/(k \times [\text{OH}^-])$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ for both catalysed (Fig. 3) and uncatalysed (Fig. 4) oxidations also indicate an inverse first order in [NaOH].

Fig. 3. Plots of (a) $1/k'$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$, (b) $1/(k' \times [\text{OH}^-])$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ (catalysed).

TABLE 3

[Chloramine-T] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [Aspartic acid] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, Temp. = 35°

[NaOH] $\times 10^2$ M	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k \times [\text{NaOH}] \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ mol}$	$k^* \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k^* \times [\text{NaOH}] \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ mol}$
5.6	—	—	5.82	3.26
6.0	—	—	5.37	3.23
6.4	—	—	4.98	3.19
6.8	—	—	4.61	3.13
7.2	1.83	1.31	4.04	2.91
7.6	1.71	1.29	3.74	2.84
8.0	1.61	1.28	3.52	2.81
8.4	1.59	1.33	3.46	2.91
8.8	1.58	1.39	3.35	2.95
9.2	1.49	1.37	3.21	2.95

* First order rate constant for Hg^{II}-catalysed reaction at [HgCl₂] = 4.0×10^{-4} M

Fig. 4. Plots of (a) $1/k$ vs $[OH^-]$, (b), $1/(k \times [OH^-])$ vs $[OH^-]$ (uncatalysed).

HgCl₂ dependence : The first order rate constants obtained for a wide range of Hg^{II} concentration ($2.0-11.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) were plotted against Hg^{II} concentration (Fig. 5). At all concentrations of Hg^{II}, rate constant increases in a linear manner with the increase in catalyst concentration. Furthermore,

Fig. 5. Plot showing the first order dependence on $[Hg^{II}]$.

the extrapolation of the curve to zero Hg^{II} concentration axis cuts an intercept on rate constant axis, which corresponds to the value of uncatalysed reaction rate constant. Thus it may be concluded that the observed rate constant is comprised of two terms and can be expressed as

$$k' = k + k'_0 [Hg^{II}]$$

where, k is the rate constant for uncatalysed oxidation and k'_0 for Hg^{II}-catalysed oxidation. The possible value of k'_0 calculated from the slope of the curve is $5.40 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

Ionic strength dependence : The effect of ionic strength variation both on uncatalysed and Hg^{II}-catalysed reactions was investigated by using neutral salts, such as NH_4Cl , $NaNO_3$, K_2SO_4 and $Ba(NO_3)_2$. The specific rate was found to be independent of the added salts concentration.

Temperature effect : To calculate the activation parameters, *i.e.* energy of activation, heat of activation, frequency factor, entropy of activation, free

energy of activation *etc.*, the kinetic runs were made at temperature range $35-55^\circ$. The values for uncatalysed reaction being $E^* = 19.8 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 19.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $A = 3.2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -15.2 \text{ e.u.}$ and $\Delta F^\ddagger = 24.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$; and for Hg^{II}-catalysed, $E^* = 17.4$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 16.7$, $A = 1.3 \times 10^{-9}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -21.6$ and $\Delta F^\ddagger = 23.6$.

Stoichiometry and products : The stoichiometry was also determined to substantiate the reaction mechanism. The results indicate that one mole of substrate reacts with the two moles of chloramine-T. The reaction step proposed are

α -Cyano acetic acid as the end-product in the reaction mixture has been confirmed by conventional analytical methods⁹. Dakin¹⁰ in his inceptive investigations had also ascertained that when two moles of chloramine-T are consumed by one mole of amino acid nitriles were the final end-products.

Discussion

A negligible salt-effect led us to conclude that the reaction must have taken place between a neutral molecule and anion¹¹. The substrate aspartic acid (S) in such an alkaline solution must be present as its anion (S⁻) and, therefore, its interaction with a chloramine-T (CAT) molecule or with its hydrolysed form *p*-toluenesulphochloramide (CAT') must occur. The following mechanism is proposed. The initial step is the hydrolysis of chloramine-T (CAT) to *p*-toluenesulphochloramide (CAT'),

The inverse first order dependence of the reaction on alkali concentration indicates that the hydrolysed product of chloramine-T (CAT), *i.e.* *p*-toluenesulphochloramide (CAT') involves as the predominant oxidising species in the oxidation reaction. Thus, CAT' molecule attacks the substrate anion producing intermediate (X) in rate-determining step which in turn interacts with another molecule of CAT' to

yield the reaction product in a fast step,

The rate expression for the disappearance of CAT is derived by applying steady-state treatment as

$$-d[CAT]/dt = \frac{k_1[CAT][H_2O] - k_{-1}[CAT'][NaOH]}{k_{-1}[CAT][H_2O] - k_{-1}[CAT'][NaOH]} \quad (A)$$

Again, on applying steady-state treatment for CAT', the rate of formation of CAT' can be equated with the rate of its consumption, therefore,

$$k_1[CAT][H_2O] = \frac{k_2[CAT][H_2O]}{k_{-1}[CAT'][NaOH] + 2k_3[CAT'][S^-]} \quad (B)$$

The expression (B) gives the concentration of CAT' as

$$[CAT'] = \frac{k_1[CAT][H_2O]}{k_{-1}[NaOH] + 2k_3[S^-]} \quad (C)$$

This value of [CAT'] is substituted in expression (A) to get

$$-d[CAT]/dt = \frac{2k_1k_2[CAT][H_2O][S^-]}{k_{-1}[NaOH] + 2k_3[S^-]} \quad (D)$$

The experimental observations show that $k_2 \ll k_{-1}$, because the rate-determining step is slowest, then

$$2k_3[S^-] \ll k_{-1}[NaOH]$$

Therefore, expression (D) takes the form as

$$-d[CAT]/dt = \frac{2k_1k_2[CAT][S^-][H_2O]}{k_{-1}[NaOH]}$$

or

$$-d[CAT]/dt = \frac{k[CAT][S^-]}{[NaOH]} \quad (E)$$

$$\text{where, } k = \frac{2k_1k_2[H_2O]}{k_{-1}}$$

where, k is the rate constant for uncatalysed oxidation reaction. The aspartic acid (S) anion reacts with Hg^{II} ion reversibly and slowly generating $Hg.S$ (Complex)¹⁹

Along with the reaction sequences (2) and (3), the following steps also occur simultaneously,

On applying steady-state treatment to steps (1), (2), (3), (5) and (6), the following rate expression is obtained,

$$-d[CAT]/dt = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[CAT][S^-]}{[NaOH]} + \frac{2k_3k_4}{k_{-1}} \frac{[CAT][Hg.S^-]}{[NaOH]} \quad (F)$$

Now from equation (4),

$$[Hg.S^-] = \frac{k_4}{k_{-4}} [Hg^{II}][S^-]$$

This value of [Hg.S⁻] is substituted in expression (F) to get,

$$-d[CAT]/dt = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{[CAT][S^-]}{[NaOH]} \left\{ 1 + \frac{k_3k_4}{k_{-4}} [Hg^{II}] \right\} \quad (G)$$

Thus, the catalysed reaction rate constant k' is comprised of

$$k' = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_{-1}} + \frac{2k_1k_2k_3}{k_{-1}k_{-4}}$$

The expression (G) shows a linear dependence of rate on Hg^{II} concentration. It also explains the non-zero intercept on rate constant axis of plots between rate constant value and Hg^{II} concentration.

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